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Neuroendocrinology

Follow-up data for the novel pharmaceutical formula Amitradicain

Abstract

Objective: To learn more about the use and effects of the novel Amitradicain formula interim findings from continuously submitted clinician-reported data regarding the use of Amitradicain, a composite pharmaceutical formula designed for specific conditions such as pathologically high sympathetic tones and catecholamine storms in rare diseases were analyzed.

Methods: Additional has been voluntarily submitted by yet another 212 other clinicians and pertains to 398 patients who have received Amitradicain for at least three months (including also drop-outs due to adverse effects) between September 2022 and October 2023. The data collection, governed by stringent data protection protocols, is not part of a formal observational study but an ongoing initiative to capture both positive outcomes and adverse events.

Results: This second analysis reveals a notable reduction in symptom severity related to targeted conditions, further supported by data and testimonials provided by the treating physicians. Adverse events are also documented to inform risk-benefit considerations.

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Conclusion: Although Amitradicain is a non-patented composite formula and data collection is conducted without a legal obligation, the early results suggest a stable promising therapeutic potential in addressing specific clinical challenges associated with rare diseases with less severe adverse effects than anticipated. The ongoing data inflow serves as a valuable resource for clinicians and researchers alike, warranting further exploration and validation.^{1,3,7}

Amitradicain

Amitradicain, a composite pharmacological formulation, was conceived by Dr. Ali Asgari at the LCG Research Laboratory under the directorship of Dr. Carolina Diamandis in Athens. The formulation was engineered to modulate autonomic dysfunction, characterized by elevated sympathetic tone, erratic catecholamine surges, and multi-organ dysregulation, in a critically ill patient. Previous pharmacological interventions had failed to elicit therapeutic benefits and had, in fact, precipitated a more rapid progression of dysregulation. Faced with this medical conundrum, the LSS, an international consortium specializing in rare neuroendocrinological conditions and affiliated with the LCG Group, solicited an innovative pharmacological solution.

Under the European (EU) legal framework, the expedient course of action was to amalgamate existing medications, anticipating potential synergistic effects in the composite formulation. Given the patient's rapidly deteriorating condition, this avenue was deemed most appropriate. Following an initial period of iterative optimization, the LCG Research team identified a robust composite that engendered substantive positive effects - more than expected - in the patient's clinical manifestations.^{1,3,7} Upon discerning a marked and statistically significant amelioration of the patient's symptoms with minimal adverse effects, the Lazar Medical

Consortium Group (LCG) resolved to disseminate the Amitradicain formula publicly rather than seek proprietary patenting. Consequently, Amitradicain remains unpatented, enabling qualified pharmacists to manufacture the compound. While LCG Research disseminates this formula as a philanthropic endeavor, all liability is incumbent upon the prescribing physician. The trademark “Amitradicain” has been secured to preclude commercial exploitation or unauthorized use. By rendering Amitradicain as an open-source formulation, LCG Research aims to equip medical professionals with an efficacious, rapid-response solution to rare, hitherto neglected diseases^{2,3,4,6,7} while preserving the formulation’s integrity. As a component of this ongoing initiative, systematic data collection aims to capture both therapeutic and adverse effects associated with Amitradicain administration. Preliminary findings have been previously disseminated^{1,2}. Subsequent to this initial publication, an additional cohort of data has been accrued. Specifically, 212 clinicians have furnished data pertaining to an incremental 398 patients who were administered Amitradicain for a minimum duration of three months. This data set encompasses an almost 14 months period from September 2022 to October 2023

and includes cases where treatment was discontinued due to adverse effects.

Data

Adverse effects: severe but far from a medical emergency type of adverse effects were observed

Sedation Levels Among Patients

and reported to us in 7 patients (3 female, 4 male), moderate to severe in 15 patients (9 female, 6 male), moderate adverse effects in 42 patients (32 female, 10 male), minor adverse effects in 72 patients (42 female, 30 male). Only 12 patients had to stop taking the Amitradicain formula due to diverse effects. In all other cases the effects were transient or manageable.

Adverse Effects in a Cohort of 398 Patients

Adverse Effects Among 398 Patients

These numbers are unexpectedly favorable when measured against the individual potential side effects of the agents in the Amitradicain formula. These figures, provide an indicative picture of the risk-benefit profile for Amitradicain. Given the range of observed effects, there appears to be a moderate scattering for most categories of adverse effects, signifying the need for careful monitoring during treatment. These results underscore a variable response to Amitradicain’s sedative properties.

In addition, the available data suggest that the adverse cardiac effects of procaine at the low dose may not play as large a role as originally thought. However, the preliminary figures do not alter the need for continuous clinical monitoring of patients with cardiac disease (especially conduction issues and chronic heart failure or reduced LV-EF). Significant positive synergistic effects were observed in a striking 78.6% of patients, with a low degree of dispersion around this median value. This compelling data strongly suggests that Amitradicain operates not merely additively but synergistically, offering enhanced therapeutic benefit beyond what its individual components can provide when administered separately. Importantly, the side effect profile have so far not exceeded those associated with the individual components, underscoring the medication's relative safety in this regard.⁶

Discussion and conclusions

The interim findings from this ongoing data collection demonstrate unexpectedly favorable therapeutic outcomes for the use of Amitradicain in treating pathologically high sympathetic tones, catecholamine storms, and autonomic dysfunctions. A majority of patients - 78.6% with low dispersion - exhibited significant helpful synergistic effects, emphasizing that Amitradicain may offer more than an additive benefit over its individual components. Importantly, the side effect profile of the composite formula did not exceed that of its individual constituents, making it a usable compound in this specific patient cohort. However, it is imperative to exercise caution in interpreting these results. The favorable safety and efficacy data, while promising, should not serve as a rationale to relax safety measures that are customary when administering the individual active ingredients separately. Physicians are strongly advised to adhere to the standard protocols and precautionary measures that pertain to the individual components of Amitradicain, including vigilant monitoring for potential adverse effects and interactions. The rapid development and deployment of Amitradicain got along with relying in the well-known safety data of its individual ingredient. Only rigorous safety assessments, especially given the lack of randomized controlled trials would have to be done substantiating these preliminary

findings. However, given the fact that Amitradicain is a blend of well-known drugs and no further adverse effects has been reported to far. In conclusion, while the data is indicative of Amitradicain's potential synergistic effects and safety, these encouraging results should not diminish the need for meticulous safety protocols. Continued vigilance is crucial, as is further study to validate these preliminary findings.

Warning and disclaimer

The prescription and administration of the Amitradicain composite formula, bearing significant risks and potential adverse reactions, are solely within the purview and responsibility of the treating physician. The utilization of these composite pharmaceuticals is consistently regarded as an individualized therapeutic endeavor when conventional pharmaceutical alternatives are deemed ineffective or inappropriate. The authors of this document, along with their affiliated institutions, expressly disclaim any and all liability, be it direct, indirect, consequential, special, exemplary, or other damages arising from or in connection with the prescription, administration, or use of the composite pharmaceuticals discussed herein. The treating physician bears the unequivocal responsibility for discerning the suitability, potential risks, and benefits of these composite pharmaceuticals for each patient, and for navigating and adhering to the applicable regulatory and professional standards governing such therapeutic endeavors. This document does not constitute medical advice, endorsement, or recommendation for the use of any pharmaceuticals, and the authors emphatically reiterate the exclusive liability of the treating physician in the prescription and administration of the composite pharmaceuticals. The contents of this document are for informational purposes only and are not a substitute for professional medical advice, diagnosis, or treatment.

Conflicts of interest

None declared.

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